

The Global Migration Crisis and Africa: a Case Study of Nigerian Migrants in Europe

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Abstract

This study assesses the global migration crisis and the Africans migration to Europe with specific focus on Nigerian migrants through the Libya-Mediterranean route and their choosing of Sweden as preferred destination over other European countries. The research study made use of secondary source of data collection, hence, data from the secondary sources were subjected to qualitative content analysis, with the main purpose of assessing the justification of these migrants leaving the country to Europe despite the numerous attendant risks and challenges they face on enroute to Europe through the Libya-Mediterranean Sea. With the use of Ernest Ravestien Pull and Push theory as the theoretical framework, this study provides a qualitative analysis of the reasons why Nigerian migrants chose to follow the Libya-Mediterranean routes to Europe and how they ended up in Sweden. The findings showed, among others, that political instability, wars, economic crisis, terrorism, insecurity, and stringent law against the fundamental human rights are factors that could make some Nigerians migrate to Europe for a better life following the Libya-Mediterranean route. The study recommended, among others, that they should be massive investment in Africa (Nigeria) across various sectors that create employment and related opportunities, as well as bring cessation to every form of insecurity and war in the continent.

1.1 Background to the Study

The surging and very much dangerous migration of African people to European countries specifically through the Libya-Mediterranean route has been a prevailing issue in both continents over the last few decades as the number of migrants increased more significantly. This mass exodus of Africans has negatively affected the social,

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economic, political and security conditions of European countries, which has necessitated the prioritization of policy reform to curb migration and refugee crises (Bark, 2015, Jose Manuel, 2017). The influx of thousands of immigrants to Europe every year mainly originates from the Middle East, South Asia, and Africa (UNHCR, 2015); hence, European countries are experiencing difficulties to meet and maintain the EU standards for receiving, facilitating asylum applications, and accommodating immigrants (Fratzke, 2015). As African leaders continue to fail in providing basic needs, infrastructure and amenities for the citizens of their various countries, the negative impacts are reflective on the continent of Europe and also in the increased numbers in deaths of Africans who journey through the Libya-Mediterranean route in search for a better life in Europe (Telschow, 2019).

According to Garcia and Martin (2015), the European government is actively making efforts to reduce the numbers of African asylum seekers who come to Europe through the Libya-Mediterranean route by collaborating with African governments to address that irregular migration problems and also provide higher education, job opportunities, and technological skills for Africans in Africa. These joint efforts have been productive according to recent BBC report (2020) and UNHCR (2020) on migration, as the number of African migrants to Europe has greatly reduced between the years of 2013 and 2020.

As global news outlets and humanitarian institution discuss this phenomenon with different statistical records as backup, a certain image and perception of African migrants is being created based on three major assumptions. Africans have been assumed to migrate to Europe mainly because of poverty, lack of opportunities and general violence (IOM, 2017). According to De Haas and Flahaux (2016), these biased assumptions are problematic because they lack sound empirical evidence as Europe is not the only destination African migrants aim for, and more reasons and experience are involved in the migrants' decision but excluded in media narratives. The argument about how Africa-Europe migration is portrayed in the media and also the global perception it creates could continue indefinitely from different scholars. As for the African migrants who experience unimaginable and despicable horrors in Libya while they journey to seek charity for their basic human needs and rights in European countries (UNSMIL and

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OHCHR, 2018), one could argue using the phrase "charity begins at home". The African irregular migration problem to Europe could ultimately be solved from the migrants' different countries in Africa by the leaders in government, and if doubt is entertained or barrier persists in achieving true governance from African leaders; perhaps it is time for a real political revolution. According to the European Commission Report (2018), migrants and refugees spread through different countries in Europe – example, Italy that has experienced large numbers of migrants who arrived at their shores over the years; Spain and Greece have recorded significant numbers of migrants seeking refuge. IOM report (2019) states that between 2017 and 2019, countries such as Syria, Ethiopia, Nigeria, Gambia, Somalia, Bangladesh and Sudan have been recorded to be that with the largest origin of migrants who arrived in Italy.

The problem under study is the recent significance increase of African migrants in Europe, particularly Nigerians, who passed through the Libya-Mediterranean route into further Europe with overwhelming risk and consequences, and ended up mostly in Sweden as asylum seekers or refugees. A total of 5000 Nigerian migrants have sought for asylum between the years 2015 and 2020 (IOM, 2021).

Generally, the migration of people from different afflicted countries around the world into Sweden has increased over the past years as she received more numbers of refugees per capital than any Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries; and this phenomenon has become a major political, economic, social, and humanitarian challenges for the Swedish government. This may be as a result of the European restrictions on the processes of inward migration which has compelled desperate African migrants to devise alternative route into European. The Libya-Mediterranean route in recent years is the most prevalent and dangerous cross-over path thousands of Africans take to Europe, more especially migrants from northern and western part of Africa with Nigeria making up the larger number.

This paper, therefore, is specifically about the migration of Nigerians to Europe through the Libya-Mediterranean route. It examines the reasons behind the decision of Nigerian migrants who choose to follow the Libya-Mediterranean route to Europe with a focus on Sweden and not other European countries like Great Britain where English is the official language just like it is in Nigeria. An in-depth qualitative analysis and subsequent conclusion would be made based on secondary data collected.

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Objective of the Paper

The main objective of this paper is to give a qualitative analysis on the migration issue of Nigerians who left to Europe through the Libya-Mediterranean route and ended up in Sweden. The specific objectives therefore, are to:

- i. Examine the causes of Nigerians migration to Europe
- ii. Find out the reasons Nigerians choose Sweden over other Europeans countries
- iii. Evaluate how they ended up in Sweden

Review of Extant literature

Transnational Migration in Africa: Historical Antecedents

Historical evidence continues to indicate that Africans traveled into, and had academic, religious and business relations with Europe (Berg, 2008: Isichei, 1983: Akanle, 2013), the Middle East, and the Gulf areas before, during, and after the double tragedies of slavery-trans-Saharan and trans-Atlantic phenomena (see Murray, 1989), and Colonization-Arab and Western colonization. Although it was not clear through archeological findings how the Negroid people arrived in Southern Europe, evidence has indicated their presence in Asia, the Middle East, and Southern Europe prior to the 15th through 16th century trans-Atlantic slave trade (Akanle, 2013). In fact, in a recent work on *The Africanity of Spain*, Toasije (2009) succinctly problematizes the systematic expunging of contributions of the pre-historic African settlers to the historical development of Iberian Peninsula by the contemporary European Spanish authorities, arguing that;

African peoples have an ancient presence in the Iberian Peninsula. In fact, Spanish identity, especially, has been forged on the frontlines of African and European interaction. Iberians from Africa and Celts from Central Europe were the two major peoples in the protohistoric times and their encounter came to create the so called Celt-Iberians. It was the natural mixture of influences. Later, in the Iberian Peninsula, there were Phoenician and Greek colonies that were replaced by the collision between the Carthaginians from Africa and the

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Romans from Europe during the wars between Rome and Carthage from 264 to 146 BC (Toasije, 2009, p. 348).

Toasije's work is relevant to this paper for its critical exposition of the disruptions perpetuated to existing socio-cultural systems of developing states by globalization, which in itself is colonization in disguise. Toasije explores the historiography of Afro-European relations in the Spanish history and the contributions of African Spaniards to the socio-cultural development of Spain. He touches on the social and cultural Europeanization of Spain perpetuated by the Spanish authorities, especially by the government and the media through racialization and criminalization of African migrants in the country. By relating the struggle of Africans currently living in Spain to the collective struggles of Africans in Europe, Toasije intimates that the entrance of Spain into the European Common Market and its emergence as a fully 'advanced' capitalist country, with bitter anti-immigrant policies, raises concern. He criticizes the move by Spanish authorities to oversee the possible obliteration from scholarly debates and social equation of the 'Africanitized' Spain as well as the contributions of African-Spaniards to the socio-cultural history of the country. Toasije's work draws essentially from the Spanish historiography, yet, it is not different from the rest of the works on Africa-Europe migration. It was obviously not directed to demographic details of migrant individuals arriving in Europe from Africa, which means the emphasis is still on adult migrants. However, it hinted about the EU's exertion of mortal force to repress the inflow of immigrants into Spain and other EU countries using the military and leaders of North African countries. Berg's (2008).

Crossing Boundaries is a review of Natalie Zemon Davis's *Trickster Travels*, an ethnographic narrative of a pre-colonial African scholar, geographer, traveler, and business man, Al Hasan ibn Muhammad ibn Ahmad, later to be called Leo Africanus. Al-Wazzan (leo Africanus), who migrated throughout Africa and was later captured by Spanish pirates, also traveled and lived in Europe over a long period of time. The importance of Berg's work to this segment of the review is its challenge of the dominant views of a socio-politically and economically reclusive and dormant pre-colonial Africa. It also captures the regional and traditional diplomatic religions and migration

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that were in existence between Europe and the pre-colonial Spain. The synopsis reads in part;

For Al-Wazzan, the embrace of Islam provided a unity, but it was the movement and mixture of peoples that held his Africa together. It was a territory of trade relations and political relations including warfare, domination and tribute. To most Europeans, by contrast, Africa was 'the other', 'a continent of extremes in the European Imagination'. Al-Wazzan provided Europeans with a different Africa, one of vast spaces populated by 'people whom everyday lives in towns, villages, mountains, and sands', he chronicled in fascinating detail (p. 230).

The history of African migration has thus been chartered by commerce, inter-ethnic wars and diplomatic engagements of leaders of the various ethnic groups on the continent, and could therefore, be said to be mostly an internal flight-alternative of displaced individuals and official engagement opportunities for ruling political authorities. It implies that pre-colonial African intra and inter-national migration could be categorized voluntary and sometimes involuntary (Akanle, 2013). The greatest known as of forced migration of Africans was perpetuated by slave trade. While many scholars have deliberately overlooked the impact of Arabic colonization and trans-Saharan trade on the continent, this review recalls that the most heinous crimes of forced migration were enacted during trans-Saharan slavery (Murray, 1989, Osahon, 2009). And the enormity of the indelible effects of Arab (Islamic) hegemony in Africa has been so subtle and insidious that new generation Africans subsume the colonizer's cultures in African heritages. In Northern Nigeria, for instance, Arab and Islamic colonization existed for upwards of 300 years prior to the trans-Atlantic slave trade and Western colonization (Fafunwa, 1974; Isichei, 1981, Nwalutu, 2004). Many Africans were pillaged across the trans-Saharan highways and marketed as slaves to Europe and the Middle East (Osahon, 2009). And the same dehumanizing theorizations and philosophical defenses of the act of slavery perpetuated by such renowned Western philosophers as David Hume, Fredrick Hegel, Montesquieu, and Roussea against Africa

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and Africans (Yelvington, 2001) were also advanced by Arabic (Islamic) writers (see Murray, 1989, Osahon, 2009). It is equally important to stress that the trans-Atlantic slave trade significantly influenced the rate of forced migration recorded in the pre-colonial African continent. It is debated that between six and 30 million Africans were forcefully ferried across the Atlantic to Europe and the New World during the trans-Atlantic slave trade (Akanle, 2013).

Drawing largely from the literature on transnational mobility, it is important to highlight that economy-induced transnational migration had occurred in many African geo-ethnic spaces before the Atlantic slave trade and colonization. For instance, Akanle (2013) cites the migration of the “Ejigbo people of contemporary South-Western Nigeria [into] Cote d'Ivoire; the Ogbomoso people of contemporary South-Western Nigeria into Ghana and the Igbos of contemporary South-Eastern Nigeria into the coastal areas of West Africa” (p. 12; see also Olutayo, 1999). These are concerned with adult migration and are specific to intra-continental migration. Toasije (2009) also points to the prehistoric movement of peoples of African descent into the Iberian Peninsula in the present day Spain, in Europe. A closer examination of the work of Olutayo (1999) indicates that migration from Africa to Europe, youth and transnational migration, economy-induced migration among the Igbo peoples of Eastern Nigeria started in the early 1800s (p. 153). The above citations are indications that voluntary and forced regional and transnational migrations are not new trends in African migration, although the patterns and causes might differ. The disruptions imposed by colonization to the existing cultural and socio-economic structures in colonized environments also meant subversion of the Indigenous peoples' means of livelihood, compelling many to seek solace in white-collar jobs. The socio-cultural inclination of as many as secure these opportunities eventually are unwittingly transformed into, and encapsulated by the colonizers' worldviews, which in turn induces the desire to migrate because they might no longer find themselves relevant in their indigenous geo-cultural spaces (Lebakeng, 2010; Sassen, 1988; Valiani, 2012). Pre-colonial and colonial migration in Africa is beyond the scope of this thesis, so my review will rather focus on the current trends in transnational migration as they relate to the youth migrant subjects.

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Colonization, political instability, and social unrest as well as natural and human-made disasters might be uppermost in the lists of current drives for the trend and size of emigration from Africa to other continents (Ratha, Mohapatra, Ozden, Plaza, Shaw, & Shimeles, 2011; Chua, 2003; Simms, 2009; Sassen, 1988). According to the literature on African migration, with the exception of education-driven migration, the majority of post-independence African migrants were initially content with regional migration (Adepoju, 2008b; Falola & Afolabi, 2007; IOM, 2009; Ratha, Mohapatra, Ozden, Plaza, Shaw, and Shimeles, 2011; Ndao, 2012; Berriane & de Hass, 2012). Transnational migration in the 21st century Africa might be informed by a myriad of factors. And as a hot topic in the social science debate, scholars have reasoned that intra-continental or regional migration still trumps Africa to Europe, youth and transnational migration accounts for a larger percentage of the movement of peoples of African descent across national borders (de Haas, 2007; TOM, 2009, Ndao, 2012).

Nigerian Youth and Transnational Migration

Nigeria has in recent times witnessed a high influx of immigrants from its neighboring Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) member nations as of the intra-continental migration that is equally ongoing in Africa (Adepoju, 2000; PP8a; Akanle, 2013; Berriane, Aderghal, & Amzil, 2012). Recent documentation, however, reveals that more people emigrate from Nigeria to overseas countries than the recorded number of immigrants coming into the country (Afolayan, 2009). It is important to highlight that the categories of potential emigrating Nigerians are more of educated professionals (Falola and Afolabi, 2007) as consistent with Sassen's research (2003), as well as indigent youth with low level of education who are unable to procure necessary document (Braht; 2012; Ndao, 2012; Nwalutu, 2014). A Nigerian profile on migration published in 2009 by the International Organization for Migration (IOM) streamlined efforts by the government and other stakeholders to regulate and manage migration processes so as to channel their positive outcomes towards development. However, the high rate of irregular migration in the West African sub-region and inadequacies of documentation equally mean that regulating emigration will remain as much of an uphill task as restrictions on immigration itself. The record level of migration activities in the

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country has been attributed to several factors, including its ever-rising population, the fluctuating economic atmosphere, and the porosity of the nation's borders - all of which might be part of the push factors paradigm. Interestingly, and crucial to my thesis, is the understanding that with its burgeoning population, Nigeria has been declared a youthful nation in studies and reports published by the United Nations and other international bodies (World Economic Forum, 2014; Zuberna, 2012). A publication of the World Economic Forum on Nigerian demographic and economic prospects reads in part;

With an estimated population of 170 million people, Nigeria is the seventh most populous country in the world. The country has a very youthful age structure, with nearly three-quarters of its population under the age of 30. Even if its fertility and mortality rates decline substantially, Nigeria will still have a youthful age structure which is projected to increase by 40% by 2025 (Global Agenda, 2014, p.3).

The obvious implication of this demographic report is that youth comprise a larger percentage of emigrants leaving the country for overseas or other regional destinations. Moreover, recent records have shown a steady rise in the number of Nigerian youth emigrating for education purposes. It is also important to note that, among the positive effects of the upsurge in migration in Nigeria, there have been a dramatic rise in the flow of official fiscal remittances into the country (Falola & Folabi, 2007; Afolayan, 2009; Akanle, 2013). For instance, a significant rise in remittances from two billion to 17 billion Dollars was recorded between the years 2004 and 2007, and in 2007 specifically, remittances from Nigerian nationals overseas accounted for 6.7% of the country's gross domestic product (Afolayii, 2009). Though the implications of the mass exodus of youth from the population of Nigeria is farther away from the scope of this thesis, but understanding the lived experiences of these migrants from origin through transit to their destination remains, in so many ways, critical to the efforts to evolve youth-friendly border policies and praxis to support the rising trend of global youth migration.

Perspectives on Youth Migration: Factors that Drive Youth to Cross International Borders as Independent Migrants

In a study, “Identifying the global potential migrants, where they want to go, and why it matters”, Esipova, Ray, and Srinivasan (2010) noted from a survey on youth migration conducted by Gallup from all the regions of the world that “factors that fuel the desire to leave one's country vary by country, region, and human development level, but a common theme is opportunity - whether it is the chance to reunite with family members who are already abroad, to start a new business, to feel free to express one's views without fear, or to live where children are treated with respect” (p. 19). As earlier stressed, the predominant emphasis is on migration and the migrant decisions and experiences of adults, while youth and children are accounted for (as is the case here) only as reuniting with family members who are economically established abroad. This discursive approach does not take into account the sheer size of youth migrants admitted to currently represent the largest segment of the 21st century global migrant population. The most salient of the survey's findings is the positive correlation between the existence of transnational social network and the people's desire to migrate. In other words, a potential youth migrant develops the desire to travel and live overseas after listening to the experiences of family members, friends or others who have traveled overseas. Thus, one's social network becomes a kind of bolster of confidence for the potential youth migrant to explore the overseas option (Akanle, 2013). While Esipova, Ray, and Srinivasan (2010) framed their survey around discourses of 'push and pull' experiences, other scholars such as Sassen (1988), Valiani (2012), and Appadurai (1996) have expressed views that made the findings very parochial for understanding the complexity of 21st century migration. However, it is particularly with respect to the migration of young adults that the work of Esipova, Ray, and Srinivasan (2010) is crucial to this study. For instance, the observation that the quest for overseas employment opportunities is a determining factor only for older adults to migrate (Esipova, Ray, & Srinivasan, 2010) is in sharp contrast to earlier findings that generalized this factor as a key motivation for migration. The study reasons that;

In Europe, the Middle East and North African region, and the Americas, older, underemployed adults aged 30 to 65 are more

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likely to say they would like to migrate than those who are the same age and are employed or not in the workforce. Millions of young people worldwide would move away from their countries permanently if they had the opportunity, regardless of whether they have jobs at home. In most places, except the Middle East and North Africa, Gallup finds that adults younger than 30 who are employed, underemployed or not in the workforce are equally likely to desire to migrate. (p. 18).

It is fascinating to observe from the responses in Esipova, Ray, and Srinivasan's (2010) study that are similar to other related works reviewed; employment opportunity, improved income and improved standard of living are also a crucial part of the push and pull factors underpinning Egyptian youth migration. The International Organization for Migration in Egypt conducted a survey to understand how Egyptian youth perceived the social, political, and economic future of their country and to what extent the turmoil, reform, and uncertainty might directly or indirectly influence their decision to migrate. The responses were affirmation of findings from previous surveys and the current distribution of Egyptians working abroad (Pitea & Hussain, 2011). According to the study, "young Egyptians are willing to migrate mainly to Arab countries, especially Saudi Arabia (26%), UAE (23%) and Kuwait (11%), followed by the United States (12%) and Italy (5%)" (p. 6). It is interesting to see that the current political crisis and the resulting socio-economic uncertainty in Egypt might induce adult Egyptians to migrate; and these factors do not have a significant impact on the youth decision to migrate. Fifteen percent of respondents agreed that the current situation makes them want to migrate, while forty-one per cent confirmed that the current crisis situation has little influence on their decision to migrate. An upwards of forty-four percent of respondents indicated that they had decided to migrate before the January 25, 2011 crisis. The findings of this survey challenged some of the earlier works suggesting that crisis situations in developing economies fan people's desire to migrate. While this could be true of adult migrants, the same may not be said of independent youth migrants. It is correspondingly essential to examine how these young adult migrants are received in the host countries in the context of limited access across territorial borders.

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Youth Migration in Unequal World: Patterns and Trends as Functions of a Skewed Power-play

The governments of African nations (and by extension, other sending countries of the South) wield little or no influence on welfare outcomes of their migrant citizens whose remittances have so many implications for the fiscal well-being of their domestic economies (Ratha, Mohapatra, Ozden, Plaza, Shaw, and Shimeles, 2011). They observed that information on the nature, demographic constituents of migrant subjects, impact, and patterns of migration is an indispensable precondition for improved management of migration; and such understanding is lacking among developing economies due to inadequate information on migration processes in these countries (Brachet, 2012; Ndao, 2012). On the contrary, advancements in technology, communication, and transportation in the industrialized world mean appropriate gathering, processing, use, and manipulation of data on migration to suit the parochial agenda of developed nations. The work of Ratha et al. (2011) further shows that economic prosperity and the acquisition of the colonialist form of education influence the flow and pattern of human migration from the developing South to the North. And in Appadurai's (1996) and Sassen's (1988) works, it does seem that economic considerations and leisure are the major considerations in the North-South migration, going by the earlier discussion. Ratha et al. (2011) also observe that approximately two-thirds of migrants from sub-Saharan Africa, especially migrants who are economically indigent and do not possess some recognized level of Western education, migrate to other countries in their economic region, which is consistent with Brachet (2012), Bhabha (2011), and Ndão (2012). What is not accentuated in Ratha et al. (2011) but is referred to, without deserved minutiae in Brachet (2012) and Ndao (2012) is that sub-regional migrations are often the first transit initiatives to transnational migration among indigent African youth migrants. The contribution of their work on the understanding of migration patterns and flow is the connection they make between the economic status of migrants and the destination of these migrants (Adepoju, 2008). Nevertheless, while economy might not be the sole determinant of migrant youth's transnational migration, it is a likely factor in the decision about the mode of migration to engage.

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The economic status of migrants is often one of the factors determining how far and to what destination they can go. For example, migrants from richer countries tend to migrate more to destinations outside of Africa, while potential migrants from economically disadvantaged countries choose to migrate more to their neighboring countries which they have assessed that they have more buoyant economies (Ratha et al., 2011). The argument here might apply to adult migrants, but the spontaneity and flux in the 21st century youth migration, as observable from other data sources (see Bilsborrow, 2010; Collins, 2011; Higley, Nieuwenhuysen, & Neerup, 2011; MOE, 2010), seem to contradict this claim. In fact, poor migrant youth from Eastern Europe and Asian countries as well as those from the Middle Eastern and North African countries seem to be influenced by economic status only with respect to the mode of transportation and movement they employ during their migration, but not with respect to their choice of destination countries (see Brachet, 2012; Black, Crush & Peberdy, 2007).

The outstanding thesis of the above analysis that is critical to understanding migration causes, drives, and flow (with particular reference to youth) is the revelation that current patterns and trends of migration are shifting with the demographic composition of migrants. Noteworthy also is the result of household surveys conducted in Burkina Faso, Ghana, Nigeria, and Senegal which show that “migrants tend to be young adults (two-thirds of Burkina Faso's emigrants were between the ages of 15 and 40) and male (more than 90 percent in Burkina Faso), generally with some education beyond primary school” (Brachet, 2012, p. 2). This observation is in agreement with most of the literature on national migration in this review (see Wong, 2009; IOM, 2009; Brachet, 2012; Ndao, 2012), and it grounds the urgent need to understand how the disproportionate power relations between the industrialized world and developing nations influence the cross-border experiences of transnational migrants, specifically youth migrants from the developing nations of Africa.

Trends in African Migration to Europe

Transnational gendered narratives on migration, “The Nigerian media and female migrants route to Italy from Libya” by Oloruntoba (2018) discusses national and international media reports concerning the 26 Nigerian adolescent girls between the

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ages of 14-18 who died and were washed ashore in the central Mediterranean Sea on their journey to Italy from Libya with over 400 other migrants. The authors argue that media outlets have uncritically framed and reported the narratives of rescue victims especially when they are females. Having comparatively analyzed several reports from different media outlets on the day of the incident (November 6, 2017), they argue that the gendered narratives of stories on migration gives causes for concern. They express their discontents as media reports tend to frame their narrative with themes such as “trafficking”, ‘prostitution’, and “sex slavery” while positioning the Nigerian and European governments on a pedestal of moral superiority as they plan and execute rescue programs.

MIGRATION ROUTES TO EUROPE

Source: ICIR, 2018

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Okeyim (2012) contributed substantially in the Africa-Europe migration research area. He examined the factors and causes that necessitate the massive migration of Nigerians into Europe with plans to live in Spain and hope for a better life. The author discovered that major causes of this migration are as a result of the worsening political situation in Nigeria in terms of “violence, election crises, failure of political leadership and corruption”. Furthermore, economic crises such as “unemployment, poverty, failure in the standard of living and management of government resources” are also contributing factors to the migration of many Nigerians to the European Union to live in Spain. The author stated that the Nigerian government has failed to provide core services that are critical for the survival of its citizens. The deprivations of Nigerian citizens of basic infrastructure, institutions and amenities such as “good roads, communication, electricity, water, good hospitals, recreational services and good governance” by their government have perpetuated the migration of Nigerians to Europe (Okeyim, 2012).

Gimenez-Gomez (2017) in the study, “Trends in Africans migration to Europe: Drivers beyond economic motivations” discusses the reasons behind Africa-Europe migration from a broader perspective as it analyzed the determinants of regular and irregular African migration between the years of 2000 and 2018. The study result shows that in addition to economic motivation. Other factors such as political persecution, ethnic cleansing, human rights violations, political instability and civil conflicts” also influence the decisions of migrants to embark on a journey to Europe. The author emphasizes the need for collaborative efforts by EU and respective migrant country governments to not only support economic development, but also to promote human security: human rights democracy, peace and social stability (Gimenez-Gomez 2017).

Yomi Kazeem (2018), a reporter for Quartz Africa, in his article “Chasing greener pastures: the harrowing, step-by-step story of a migrant's journey to Europe” discusses the perilous encounter of a desperate Nigerian migrant who embarked on a migration journey to Italy through Libya-Mediterranean route. According to the reporter, the migrant who got distracted by the seemingly better life in Europe dropped out of school after his lower level diploma from a polytechnic college in Edo State, Nigeria in 2011. The migrant's detailed and terrifying story covered his leaving Nigeria at first with 22 young migrants that consisted of 10 men and 12 women, after which they

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converged with hundreds of other migrants brought in by different agents. He discussed about crossing the Sahara Desert, Libyan Limbo, deadly sea and being among the very few who made it alive to Italy as many died on their way to Europe (Yomi Kazeem, 2018).

IOM (2018) extensive report, “Enabling a better understanding of migration flows from Nigeria towards Europe” comprehensively discussed and analyzed the main causes of the massive migration flows of Nigerians to European countries such as Greece and the Netherlands, transiting through Niger and Lybia. It discusses the Nigerian perception of European, their decision drivers to migrate, and graphically illustrated informative statistics of deportees and asylum seekers in European countries.

900 African Migrants mostly Nigerians Rescued in Mediterranean Arrive Italy

Source: The Whistler, 2017

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Source: The Whistler, 2021

Another collaborative report by the OHCHR and UNSMIL (2018), “Desperate and Dangerous Report on the human rights situation of migrants and refugees in Libya” focuses on examining the human rights violations most migrants and refugees undergo

in Libya during their journey across the desert and Mediterranean Sea, as well as assist to expedite the life-saving work of rescue vessels operated by humanitarian organization (OHCHR and UNSMIL, 2018).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The theory of push and pull factor is adopted in this paper. It was propounded by Ernest Ravenstien, one of the foremost British migration theorists. In this theory, he used the census population and the migration strategies of inhabitants from England and Wales to analyze the concept and context of issues surrounding migrations. In his argument, he avers that unfavorable conditions in rural areas or less developed countries push people away from their temporary places to permanent residences (Ravenstein, 1885: Obi-Ani B-Isiani, 2020). Among his instances on unfavorable conditions are high rate of unemployment, heavy taxation, high rate of mortality, wars, conflicts, abuses of human rights, food insecurity, lack of good education facilities and teachers, poor climatic conditions, flood and erosion. In contrast to these unfavorable conditions which pushes people away are the pull factors envisioned in another environment of which inhabitants convert the place as its permanent abode. These pull factors according to Obi-Ani and Isiani (2020) negates the conditions previously found by the migrants in their former residence. Some of these pull factors include good atmosphere, peaceful co-existence, food security, adequate employment, allured opportunities, provision of skills, good transportation sectors, good education, less conflicts, democratic elections, less thefts and arson as well as less means of taxation.

This theory reveals that Nigeria is descending into poverty due to poor leadership style, insecure environment, poor infrastructure, inadequate educational facilities and lack of jobs opportunities for graduates. These disjointed atmospheres motivate the youths to risk their lives in search of greener pastures in European countries where there is a high level of technological advancement, good job opportunities, education, as well as high life expectancy. Thus, in the quest to migrate to these technological driven environments, Nigerian youths suffer the loss of lives and properties having adopted harmful strategies and coping devices towards surviving in foreign lands.

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In elucidating the reasons individuals or groups move from one place to another, the paper complemented the Ravestein theory with theories of human mobility. The theory suggests that the migration of individuals or groups can be predicted and could be curtailed when issues accompanying people to move is predicted. According to Yan and Zhou's (2019), “predicting human mobility fluxes between locations is a fundamental problem of transportation science in a country or spatial economy”. This entails that individuals take full responsibility of the dangers of transportation to their destination or permanent place of abode as well as the outcome of economic advancement in the country he or she is migrating to.

In analyzing this theory as it affects this paper, migrants from Nigeria adopted different strategies such as faking individual's documents, false international passports and identity and stow away to scale to Western Europe for better opportunities. In their inability successfully to navigate the legitimate means of migration, many opt for the illegitimate path of crossing through the African desert to the Mediterranean Sea where they face the options of drowning, deportation, enslavement or incarceration. On the other hand, the survivors who managed to make it into Europe had to devise coping mechanisms of not only avoiding the security agents but also of their survival. These migrants remain helpless as their dreams and hopes of making quick health is suspended in the limbo.

The above theories explain the reasons Nigerians move from their country to another in search of greener pastures without taking cognizance of the risk involved in these illegal migration strategies. It is on this note that the study avers that there is need to restructure the socio-economic organizational sectors of the country and inward looking at the successive Nigerian leadership to devise strategies of mitigating those systemic problems that drive its citizens to look unto Europe for greener pastures. Therefore, the thrust of the paper is to fill the gap in knowledge of the debilitating economic climate prevalent in Nigeria occasioned by corrupt and inept leadership which does not allow the poor to breath that induces Nigerians to migrate to European countries.

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Nigerian Migration to European Countries

Migration from Africa to Europe continues to remain a huge challenge and threat to both continents, as thousands of migrants from sub-Saharan Africa are still making their way to Europe through Libya-Mediterranean route (Uchebora, 2016; Pew Research Centre, 2018). Specifically, the migration of Nigerians to European countries in the past years was very high, as they were majorly part of contemporary migration flows across the Mediterranean Sea (Beber and Scacco, 2018). Countries such as Spain and Italy were targeted destinations for migrants from Nigeria as they arrived in their thousands during the periods of 2016 and 2017, with the majority of them hailing from Benin City, the capital of Edo State in Nigeria (Agbakwuru, 2018).

Nigerian Migrants en-route to Europe

Source: ICIR, 2018

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They refused to deport us' – Nigerians in Libyan cell cry for help

Source: ICIR, 2018

Death of Nigerian Migrants attempting to Cross the Libyan Desert

Source: The Punch Newspaper, 2022

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The historical background of Nigerians migration to European countries could be divided into three parts which are: the pre-colonial, colonial and post-colonial era. However, this study will focus on the post-colonial era because that was when the Nigerian migration to Europe through desert and sea occurred by volition.

During the post-colonial era given the colonial ties that have been established between Britain and Nigeria, educated Nigerian elites between the periods of 1950 and 1970 began a discretionary movement to the United Kingdom and America for education, work, and business reasons of which they returned back to Nigeria in due time. The “no return” agenda and attitude among many Nigerian migrants in their destination countries in Europe and other parts of the world was a result of the economic stagnation Nigeria started to experience in the 1970s and 1980s due to political instability in the country (Okeyim, 2012). These unfortunate events have lingered and even worsened until today. As the number of Nigerian migrants increased over the decades, destination countries in Europe adapted more stringent migration policies to regulate the inflow of migrants in general, hence, Nigerian migrants became more frustrated, desperate and compelled to ply the risky Libya-Mediterranean route to get into European countries with high hopes for better livelihoods (Kate, 2017).

Causes of Nigerian Migration

Every country of the world is expected to possess and perform certain features and functions for the welfare of its citizens in order to qualify to be called a country (Okeyim, 2012). Some of these features and functions include the provision of basic job creation and employment, security, infrastructure, academic institutions, hospitals, and prioritized policies to benefit and protect its citizens. When these vital factors and necessities are lacking in a country, then the migration of its citizens is inevitable. According to the Push and Pull theory, there are eminent factors pushing migrants away from their country of origin as they seek better living conditions in the destination country that pulls them in. This theory is very applicable in the case of Nigerian migrants seeking for better lives in European countries.

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Economic Crisis

Studies have shown that the migration of Nigerians to European countries is mostly associated with economic challenges or factors such as unemployment, lack of sufficient income, lack of economic growth, financial problem and debts (Danoan, 2018; Adeniyi, 2006). Before migration, most of the Nigerian migrants were self-employed or received daily wages that were not sufficient enough for their monthly expenses (Danaan, 2018). Given the inability of the Nigerian governments to properly manage, stabilize and sustain their economies for so many years, the migration flow of their citizens to European countries has drastically increased.

The development of industries, factories, and institutions should be the priorities of the Nigerian government as it would create jobs to assimilate university graduates, and people with craftsmanship, but the UN statistics on Nigerian migration does not look like those factors have been considered (IOM, 2018). Nigeria may have been quoted in several reports, journals and news outlets to be the leading oil and gas producer in Africa (Deloitte Report, 2018), but it is apparently ironic that majority of its citizens are living in abject poverty, hash and miserable conditions as a result of greed, selfishness, and corruption of the Nigerian politicians and government (Danaan, 2018). Hence, currently, Nigeria is no longer among the fastest growing economies in Africa by percentage growth in GDP (PWC report, 2019).

Terrorism and Insecurity

One of the greatest responsibilities of the government of any country in the world is to protect the lives and properties of its citizens. If this vital necessity is lacking in a country, then what would be the fate or response of its citizens? 'Run for their dear life', a concerned individual may suggest. Thus, most Nigerian citizens resort to migrating to European countries where they hope to find security. The Nigerian government has failed to provide adequate security in some parts of the country where political and religious insurgences abound (Barungi, 2019); hence, it has precipitated the massive migration of Nigeria out of the country seeking security of their lives and families in European countries.

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The Boko Haram insurgency and violent incivility that has existed over a decade in the north-east of Nigeria still has not been completely put to a halt even as it continues to reduce and destabilize the population and political and economic activities in that region (Herbet and Husaini, 2018). Currently in Nigeria, the terrorism of the Fulani cattle herders whom some people argue is another arm of the Boko Haram terrorist group is nothing to take for granted. There have been several accounts where these groups of cattle rearers who carry AK 47 machine guns go to remote villages in the Eastern part of Nigeria raping women in farms lands as their cows eat the farmers' crops, with sporadic shooting and killing both men, women and children even in churches and schools of these communities, (Akinyetun, 2015; Ezemenaka, 2018; Amnesty International, 2018). Even the Niger Delta crisis in Nigeria that seemed calm for a while is now beginning to resurface, threatening the country if the government does not comply with their proposals for autonomy and control of the oil resources (Herbert and Husaini, 2018).

Political Instability

Nigeria has been politically unstable for many years since its independence from Britain in 1960, following the 1956 initiation of oil extraction and creation of three regional administrative divisions based on the three majority ethnic groups which include Igbo, Yoruba, and Hausa (Ajodo-Adebanjoko, 2017). This persistent challenge has been a major contributing factor to the increasing migration flow of Nigerians to European countries (Okeyim, 2012). Seven years after Nigerian independence, she experienced a bloody civil war, the Biafran war, which lasted for three years (1967-1970). Also, within and after those years, there have been a series of religious crises inter-tribal conflicts, failure of political leadership, uncertainty in future government, demonstrations, military coups, political turmoil and violence in the country (Okeyim, 2012). These critical events contributed to the deterioration of the Nigerian political system as the then military government completely failed in their responsibility to maintain law and order in the country (Herbert and Hasaini, 2018). The political instability in Nigeria has also reflected negatively in the proper functionality of the national economy. For instance, for decades, there have been serious uprisings in the Niger Delta (oil

producing) region in Nigeria where 40 ethnic groups with their smaller populations are politically and economically marginalized (Herbert and Husain, 2018), example, Kokodiagbene community in Delta State, where Chevron is present for over 40 years; hence, militants rose and declared war against international oil companies in that region and the federal government of Nigeria for self-governance and adequate control of oil resources within their region (Okeyim, 2012). As a result of the international marginalization and total neglect of the people of Niger Delta by the Nigerian government, there have been unspeakable impoverishments, unemployed youths, lack of electricity and clean water, poverty and health issues in that region. Therefore, the people opt to migrate to European countries.

The Libya-Mediterranean Route to European

Libya is a country located in the Maghreb region in North of Africa. It is bordered by the Mediterranean Sea to the north and other surrounding countries such as Chad, Niger, Algeria, Tunisia, and Egypt. For several years, Libya has been used by thousands of migrants, particularly from Northern and Western African countries as gateway transit and destination path to Europe due to its geographic proximity and historical ties (World Migration Report, 2018). According to Kate (2017), the European restrictions on inward regular migration may have precipitated the increase of irregular migration flow into Europe through dubious and desperate means. Migrants fleeing from war, and searching for better life opportunities in European countries fall victims to human smuggling and trafficking against the promise of easy way passage across the Mediterranean Sea and national borders (MHUB, 2018). Despite the news about people who get dehumanized and die on their journey to Europe through the Libyan desert and across the Mediterranean Sea, African migrants still adamantly ply this very dangerous route that is run by organized criminal gang networks.

Sweden

With a current population of 10.2 million people and geographic space of 173,860 square meters, Sweden is the largest county in Northern Europe. According to Statistiska Centralbyran (2018), 2.5 million people out of the total population of Sweden

have a foreign background. Sweden operates a unitary form of government and is currently divided into 21 counties and 290 municipalities.

Sweden has over the years gained a global reputation for being an archetypical and homogenous welfare state until in recent decades when it began to receive a number of refugees from outside of Europe, thereby altering its demographic composition (Sanandji, 2018). This transformative phenomenon has led Sweden to the challenge of attempting to combine her socially idealized and welfare state with multi-culturalism. The irregular flow of migrants into Sweden has indeed brought about some negative impacts on their social ideologies, even though the May 2013 riots, the rise of the anti-immigration party and the tightening of border controls portray a subtler narrative of the challenging situation. (Riniolo, 2016). As a fact, Sweden has worked hard not only to receive, accommodate, and protect refugees and asylum seekers from unstable countries, but also create opportunities for migrants into the labour market (Riniolo, 2016).

Swedish Migration and Asylum Policy related to Nigerian Migrants

As Sweden struggle with an unprecedented increase of its non-western population from 2% to 15% of the total population over the past 20 years, migration and asylum policy reform are being enforced in order to regulate and manage this problematic migration inflow (Sanandaji, 2018). This aims to provide qualitative analysis of the Swedish migration and asylum policy (2018) that governs the reception and integration of refugees and migrants into the Swedish society.

The Swedish Government handling of the refugee situation

Over two decades, several approaches and changes in migration and integration policies have been adopted in handling the refugee and asylum crisis by different government administrations in Sweden. The consistent increase in the numbers of migrant population in Sweden throughout those years has been in four phases. The first phase occurred during the early 1990s when economic crises propelled refugees from the former Yagoslavia, and also the influx of refugees who fled for their lives from the Balkan areas as a result of war and arrived in Sweden for refuge. This was a very

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challenging period in Sweden as she was experiencing the highest level of unemployment since 1930 (Riniola, 2016); thus, the massive number of migrants did not equal the Swedish labour market demand (Wiesbrock, 2011). The second phase happened during the period of social Democratic government administration between the years of 1994 and 2006 which apparently led to the creation of Integration Board called “integrations verket in Sweden”. This agency was created for the purpose of promoting and monitoring the state of integration in Sweden and ensuring proper integration process of migrants into the Swedish society. Still in an effort to handle the migration crisis, the Social-Democratic government also created and enforced on act “Sweden, the future and diversity, from immigration policy to integration policy (1997/98: 6)” with policy that is based on equal rights, responsibility and opportunities for everyone, regardless of their ethnic and cultural background.

The third phase of the massive influx of migrants in Sweden was between 2006 and 2014, the period when a new reform 'Labour Market Introduction of Newly Arrived Migrants Individual Responsibility with Professional support' was made and enforced in late 2010 by the Center-Right Government, Ministry of Integration and Gender Equality and the Swedish Public Employment Service in order to manage the labour integration disparity of migrants. This reform, however, has been deemed to be catastrophic and recognized as one of the biggest problems of migrant integration in Sweden (Riniolo, 2016). The fourth phase is the recent increase in the number of migrant inflow in Sweden and the new stem approach the government has adopted in 2016 to regulate and handle the ongoing global refugee situation, such as the introduction of temporary residence permit, internal border control and limiting the right to family member immigration. With a focus on African migrants and Nigeria to be specific, the series of temporary internal border control measures adopted by the Swedish government to significantly reduce irregular migration was applicable to them until May 11, 2018. Therefore, Nigerian migrants who intend to seek asylum will not be approached or harassed by authorities to that effect but allowed to tender their cases to the Swedish migration board and hope to be granted temporary residence to stay in Sweden.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of the findings is carried out in order to address the objectives of the study. In reflection to the research questions, this study aims to find out the causes of Nigerian migration to Europe; how they ended up in Sweden, and why they chose to seek asylum in Sweden but not other countries in Europe. However, the findings obtained from the study revealed that as the Nigerian migrant evaluated their options on how to evacuate their country of origin in the most “in expensive or easier” way to Europe for a better life, they decided to journey through the Libya-Mediterranean route and somehow ended up in Sweden as their final destination country.

Just as Ravestien Push and Pull theory (Ravestien, 1885) stipulates in relation to international migration, it is evident that there are inexorable factors that pushed them out of their country of origin (Nigeria) and pulled them into their final destination country (Sweden). These factors that have pushed the migrants out of Nigerian are so crucial and frustrating that caused them to neglect the imminent risks and dangers of the intervening obstacles across the borders of Nigeria and Sweden.

According to Okeyin (2012), when a country is experiencing instability, it is likely to fail in political leadership, encourages corruption and also exhibits uncertainty in future government. This will result to subsequent failure to provide security, basic infrastructure, hospital and academic institutions for the country; hence the migration of its population for greener pastures is necessary. In other words, since the power to make impactful economic, social and technological changes in Nigeria is obtained through politics, it is difficult for every sector in Nigeria to work effectively. Thus, political instability has created the avenue for anti-progressive activities and corruption to abound in Nigeria.

The push factor of economic crisis is a major issue in Nigeria, as it is preponderant in the empirical findings of this study. The findings also reveal that there is a very high level of unemployment and joblessness amongst the college and University graduates in Nigeria, which has driven many of them into fraudulent and immoral means of survival. The positive impact or plan of the Nigerian government on how to resolve these critical issues is yet to be seen and recorded by the people; hence, thousands of Nigerians migrate to Europe following the Libya-Mediterranean pathway with hope to meet their basic needs in life.

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Terrorism and insecurity has been a push factor for many years to Nigerians who are migrating to other countries and a lot of literatures have been written about it, even as the findings of this research confirms (Herbet and Husaini, 2010; Barungi, 2017). According to the Push and Pull theory, migrants' destination country converts their push factors to pull factors. In other words, almost every factor that migrants need but lack to survive, prosper and be happy in their country of origin is provided for and exists in the destination country. In the case of this study, Sweden as the Nigerian migrants' final destination country is a more secure and safe haven for the migrants to start their lives afresh with peace of mind. The high humanitarian reputation of Sweden throughout Europe and the world, especially when it pertains to migrants, refugees' asylum seekers, is second to none. The Swedish migration and asylum police have been very accommodating for years despite the recent amendments as a result of the problematic massive inflow of migrants from different parts of the world.

Conclusion

The findings of this paper discovered that Nigeria has been politically unstable for many years since her independence from Britain in 1960, following the 1956 initiation of oil extraction and creation of three regional administrative divisions based on the three majority ethnic groups, as well as the Boko Haram insurgency, kidnapping, Biafra agitation crisis and the herder attack. These persistent challenges have been a major contributing factor to the increasing migration flow of Nigerians to European countries.

Apart from the aforementioned causes, the paper further discovered that given the inability of the Nigerian government to properly manage, stabilize and sustain its economy for so many years, the migration flow of their citizens to European countries has drastically increased.

On the choice of Sweden by Nigerians over other European States, the paper discovered that the resettlement route to live in Sweden is a form of special asylum program run collaboratively by Sweden and the UNHCR for refugees and persons eligible for subsidiary protection under the provisions of Sweden's Aliens Act. Finally, the programme applies to refugees with complicated migration cases where they can neither return to their country of origin nor give continued residence permit in the host

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country. These migrants cannot be deported for several reasons such as the fear of being subjected to death; inhumane conditions, or received corporal punishment in their country of origin; hence, Sweden creates sustainable solutions for them through resettlement programmes and following recommendation from United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR).

Recommendations

In view of the above findings, the paper recommends the following:

1. The international community should agree on a single, comprehensive narrative that would label the criminality and bring an end to modern slavery, by developing policies and frameworks to tackle the root causes of the migration crisis.
2. There should be massive investment in Africa across various sectors that create employment and related opportunities.
3. Nigerian government should endeavour to end all forms of insecurity in the country, embrace and invest more in non-traditional business models such as sports and sporting academies.
4. Increased resource allocation by governments to ministries supporting youth and gender, as they make up the largest constituent in our population thereby being the most affective.
5. Finally, a mindset shift (by young Africans especially Nigerians, which drives us to take control and responsibility for our continent) is very much required.

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